

Assessment of Stakeholder Participation in the Management of Sports Development Programs in Akwa Ibom State

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to investigate the role, level of participation, challenges and ways forward for enhancing stakeholders participation in sports development. The study sought to answer five research questions and two hypotheses regarding: the extent to which stakeholders are involved, the roles that they play in the process, how managers make decisions, barriers that prevent this from becoming a greater reality as well as what solutions can be leveraged. Method: Using a descriptive survey design, data was collected through the use of a structured questionnaire from 200 participants selected using simple random sampling techniques for the government officials, sports associations, private sector and community leaders. Descriptive statistics like mean, percentage, standard deviation and z test were used to analyze the data. The findings showed that the stakeholders had a moderate involvement in sports development with large contributions from government and sports associations. Nonetheless, challenges such as lack of good funding, improper training and conflicting property claims are obstacles to effective participation. Moreover, the study identified stakeholder participation to be dependent on clarity of roles and improved coordination. The conclusion also suggested that a more participatory based approach is necessary to consider stakeholder views and involvement in decision and project implementation. Given that stakeholder participation in sports development programs is a step to attaining the benefits of management which have been illustrated. The study recommended that regular training, the creation of a centralized coordinating body and improved transparency in decision-making process would significantly enhance the state's involvement of stakeholders within its managed sports development programs.

Keywords: Stakeholder Participation, Sports Management, Sports Development Programs, Public-Private Partnership in Sports and Community Involvement in Sports

Introduction

Sports development programs are complex entities to administer and maintain, requiring the commitment, efforts and buy-in of many sectors. Freeman (1984) argued that stakeholders, which include state institutions and governmental bodies, sports organizations-community members, the private sector, nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), have significant influence on policy formation for sport development. The inclusion of these different strands in sporting programs has heavily impacted the growth of sports programs in Akwa Ibom State. But how this participation occurs and the degree to which it is effective can, at times, hinder the achievement of desired sports development outcomes. The findings related to the behavior of stakeholder participation in sports development programs are important for improving sports policies and programs in the area.

There exists a theoretical framework in business to understand why engaging stakeholders from different groups to determine organizational goals would make sense (Freeman, 1984). It is explained that in sports management, the theory posits that active involvement of stakeholders (sports federations, local governments, educational institutions and community organizations) can improve planning, mobilization resources and execution of programs. This inclusivity prevents a mono faced approach that results in more holistic sport development strategies stemming from multiple vantage points (Chalip, 2006). But much remains unknown with regard to stakeholder involvement in sports programs in Akwa Ibom state, and it calls into question how and whether existing managerial practices impact the performance of various sporting disciplines.

The success of sports development programs relies greatly on the involvement and engagement of stakeholders in the process of decision-making. According to Hoye et al. In the words of Wicker et al. (2015), stakeholder engagement in sport organizations can foster trust, accountability, and transparency among other governance-related factors. This limited engagement of stakeholders in Akwa Ibom State can result in inefficiencies in resource allocation, poor program implementation and sustainability of sports programs. Therefore, it such crucial to evaluate the involvement of stakeholders in planning and implementation of sports development program and also the monitoring part as well, by doing this we can figure out what stakeholder is missing that should be made involved or improved.

Many studies have acknowledged the difficulties concerning stakeholder involvement in sport governance, exemplified by conflicting interests and limited sets of capacities for collaborative governance (Parent & Deephouse, 2007; Winand et al., 2013). These difficulties make it difficult to engage stakeholders effectively, particularly in developing sport regions such as Akwa Ibom State. In

order to address these challenges effectively, it is important that the roles and responsibilities of each stakeholder and their expectations are clearly identified while developing strategies to help them work together synergistically. This identification of constraints in stakeholder engagement enables policymakers and sports managers to focus on targeted interventions to improve the governance of sports programs.

A number of case studies suggest that stakeholders have been influential in shaping sports development outcomes when they are included and empowered within governance frameworks with increased levels of stakeholder participation, are more evident. For instance, Winand et al. Some relationships we know from the literature: Powell (2004) states sports development to be more sustainable if stakeholder involvement is ensured on strategic planning and decisions making processes, as those same stakeholders have higher willingness to support any program they also helped foster. In Akwa Ibom State, there exists gap with little or no empirical studies on the effect of stakeholder participation on sports development programmes. This gap in knowledge underscores the importance of further research on stakeholder contributions and challenges, applying varied custodian ships across Kerala state sports.

Therefore, a holistic review of stakeholder involvement in the management of sports development programs as a guide to policy and practice in Akwa Ibom State is required. This paper tries to fill this void by looking at the roles, level of engagement, obstacles and impacts in the administration of sports development program stakeholders in the state. It is hoped that in so doing, the research will add to our knowledge of how stakeholder engagement can be leveraged to drive better and more sustainable sports development outcomes and highlights potential implications for sports management and development studies within Nigeria.

Research Questions

To what extent are stakeholders involved in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State?

What are the roles of different stakeholders in the management of sports in Akwa Ibom State?

What is the level of participation of stakeholders in decision-making processes related to sports management in Akwa Ibom State?

What are the challenges faced by stakeholders in participating effectively in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State?

What are the strategies for improving the participation of stakeholders in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses:

Hypothesis (H₀₁): Stakeholders are not significantly involved in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State based on gender.

Hypothesis (H₀₂): The level of stakeholder participation in decision-making processes does not significantly impact sports management in Akwa Ibom State.

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

The main theoretical bases useful for understanding stakeholder participation in sports management are the concepts of participatory governance and stakeholder engagement, thereby illuminating how collaboration can be a managerial approach. The framework is built upon the principles from stakeholder theory (Freeman 1984) that argues organizations should care for and value everyone who has a stake in a particular process or outcome. The understanding is vital in the context of sports management, where a range and combination of stakeholders (e.g. government agencies, sporting bodies, local communities and private sector interests) play key parts in determining how successful sport initiatives can be set up, run and maintained (Hoye et al., 2015). In addition, the framework references participatory governance theory to support a more democratic and productive decision making process by incorporating a plurality of voices other than those typically heard in mainstream public discourse (Arnstein, 1969). This integrated approach affords a platform to study stakeholder involvement in sports development programme management particularly within areas like Akwa Ibom State.

Stakeholder Participation in Sports Management

Community involvement as a dimension of sports management can refer to the participation of all kind stakeholders in decision-making processes, planning, implementation and evaluation about sports programs and policies. For Parent and Deephouse (2007), stakeholder participation embraces more than consultation itself, including a variety of activities that involve stakeholders in the process of how sports initiatives are developed and managed. The contrary is stakeholder involvement which includes working relationships, joint decision-making and co-creation to aspire representation of interest and perspectives (O'Boyle et al., 2019). This concept is also important in sport management because it enables more shared

governance, where multiple actors (e.g., governmental agencies, sport federations, community groups and private organizations) come together to pursue common goals and advance sustainable sports development (Winand et al., 2013).

Types of Stakeholders in Sports Management

There are a host of stakeholders involved in managing sports programs, all fulfilling special functions necessary to the creation and maintenance of sport initiatives. These are groups of stakeholders like government, sports organisation, private sector companies and communities. Formulation of policies, provision of funding and regulation especially on sports development is a major role played by the government bodies through national and local sports councils (Houlihan & Green, 2010). Agents and coordinators of sports organizations deal with the direct organization and management of sports activities, events, often serving as intermediaries between athletes and their coaches and regulatory bodies (Slack & Parent, 2006).

Sponsors, corporate partners and media organisations in the private sector also have a major role when it comes to funding, marketing and promoting sports programs (Smith & Westerbeek 2007). Lastly, the community contributes to grassroots sports development by participating in local sporting events, enrolling children in sports programmes and giving feedback on how well sports programs work (Misener & Doherty, 2009). Also, the participation of all such groups is critical in sports management strategies as each group provides different kinds of resources, perspectives and expertise.

Overview of Sports Development Programs in Akwa Ibom State

The growth of Sports Development Programmes in Akwa Ibom State since then has been unprecedented and it has continued to champion grassroots development, discovery of talents as well infrastructure renovation in sporting houses. The state ministry of youth and sports is the prime government body responsible for policy formulation and overseeing sports development programs in collaboration with local sports councils, educational institutions, private sector partners (Akpan, 2020). A recent effort, the Akwa Ibom Youth Sports Festival has played a role in mobilizing youth support for participation in sports, identification of talents, and building communal passion (Ekpo & Ekong 2022).

These opportunities are suitable for young athletes by state, national and international competitions. However, there are a number of challenges that combine to reduce the efficacy of existing sports development programs in the state. In recognition of the identified issues that hinder sustainable sports

development which includes amongst others inadequate funding, dearth of infrastructures, poor stakeholder synchronisation and insufficient capacity building initiatives (Udo & Essien, 2021).

Materials and Methods

Data collected has descriptive survey design which appraised the level of participation by stakeholders in sports development programs management in Akwa Ibom State. The use of the descriptive design is suitable in collecting, analyzing and presenting data about the current practices, behaviors and attitudes of various sports management stakeholders (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The design allows the researcher to obtain information from respondents in large numbers, which supports a good overall view of stakeholder engagement when developing sports. The research took place in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The nation-state is recognized for its... (Akpan, 2020) landscape assets as well as the northward attention of each sports improvement at more than one degree in a drop within competition by way of grassroots physical games applications route and local sports activities fairs have lengthily reformed underperformance. Study Area Akwa Ibom consists of 31 Local Government Areas (LGAs), the study focused on selected LGAs with remarkable sports development programs and Stakeholder active involvement. This study targeted the population of interest through a purposive selection of relevant stakeholders in sports management in Akwa Ibom State. Among those involved are Ministry of Youth and Sports officials, local sports councils, sports club administrators, coaches, athletes, private sector partners as well as community leaders. It was estimated that a sample size of approximately 200 respondents for each stakeholder groups represent the opinion of the state, by using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. The large sample size ensures extensive coverage and allows the investigator to draw reliable inferences for the entire population.

We used a multi-stage sampling to select eligible study participant. Selection of LGAs First, purposive sampling was employed to select some LGAs that are well involved in sports development programs. Stratified sampling was then conducted to classify the stakeholders into various sectors; including government officials, sports administrators, corporate sector partners, while community people are also part in this study. Each sampling unit was further stratified, and simple random sampling was then implemented for selecting individual participants based on the stakeholder group into which they were classified. Structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The survey instrument was fashioned as a closed-ended questionnaire representing the Likert scale and queried the roles of stakeholders, levels of involvement in sports management practice, problems experienced during participation and perceptions about effectiveness of sports management practices within Akwa Ibom State. Research questions were

answered through descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean & standard deviation) whereas hypotheses were tested using Z-test (inferential statistics). This study aboffates the ethical regulatory principles which include informed consent in research, confidentiality and voluntary participation of all respondents. Prior to giving consent to participate, participants read information about the purpose of the study, procedures, potential risks and benefits. At every stage of the research, anonymity was respected and no attempt was made to use this information for anything other than academic purposes.

RESULTS

Table 1: Mean rating of the extent of stakeholders involvement in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State

S/N	Statement	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	TWS	Mean (X)
1	Stakeholders are actively involved in all phases of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State	100	80	15	5	1265	3.16
2	There is sufficient representation of all key stakeholders in sports management decision-making	90	85	20	5	1235	3.09
3	The contributions of stakeholders significantly impact sports development in Akwa Ibom State	85	90	15	10	1225	3.06
4	Stakeholders regularly participate in meetings and consultations on sports development	95	80	15	10	1230	3.08
Grand mean							3.10

An examination of stakeholder participation in sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State revealed that stakeholders input is generally view to be positive. The means showed the highest value of 3.16, indicating that stakeholders perceive themselves as very involved in all aspects of sports development This is very closely succeeded by the general impression of involvement in meetings and consultations, at a mean score of 3.08. Also respected – though slightly less — are the representation of major stakeholders in decision-making (mean = 3.09) and how much their contributions to success matter(mean = 3.06). Overall, the grand mean of 3.10 indicates that stakeholders perceive their knowledge as useful, but there may be room for greater participatory process in all cases (Table 4).

Table 2: Mean rating of the roles of different stakeholders in the management of sports in Akwa Ibom State

S/N	Statement	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	TWS	Mean (X)
1	Government officials play a critical role in formulating policies for sports development.	110	60	20	10	1270	3.18
2	The private sector contributes significantly to funding sports development programs.	95	75	20	10	1255	3.14
3	Sports associations are key players in implementing sports programs in Akwa Ibom State.	100	70	20	10	1260	3.15
4	Community members and local leaders are involved in monitoring and evaluating sports initiatives.	90	80	20	10	1230	3.08
Grand Mean						3.14	

The table indicates a generally strong perception of stakeholder roles in sports management in Akwa Ibom State. The highest mean score (3.18) suggests that government officials are seen as crucial in policy formulation for sports development. The private sector's role in funding (mean = 3.14) and sports associations' involvement in implementing programs (mean = 3.15) are also acknowledged positively. Community members and local leaders have a slightly lower perception in their monitoring and evaluation role (mean = 3.08). Overall, with a grand mean of 3.14, stakeholder roles are viewed positively, highlighting significant contributions across sectors.

Table 3: Mean rating of stakeholders level of participation in decision-making processes related to sports management in Akwa Ibom State

S/N	Statement	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	TWS	Mean (X)
1	Stakeholders are adequately informed about decision-making processes in sports development programs.	105	65	20	10	1265	3.16
2	Stakeholders have opportunities to contribute to decisions related to resource allocation for sports programs.	95	80	15	10	1255	3.14
3	Stakeholders are involved in evaluating the outcomes of sports development projects.	100	75	15	10	1260	3.15
4	The opinions of all stakeholders are considered in major sports management decisions.	90	85	15	10	1245	3.11
Grand Mean						3.14	

The data shows that respondents have a sense of inclusion in the decision-making processes with respect to sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State. Of note, only stakeholders report thinking they are adequately informed on how decisions are made, receiving a mean score of 3.16. Finally, their capacity for resource allocation (mean = 3.14) and participation in output evaluation of sports development are scored fairly similarly (mean = 3.15). However, the administration scored lowest (mean = 3.11) on considering stakeholder opinions in major decisions. The results therefore indicate that stakeholders are heavily involved in decision-making (grand mean = 3.14), albeit there is scope for inclusivity to be strengthened during the formulation of major decisions.

Table 4: Mean rating of challenges faced by stakeholders in participating effectively in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State

S/N	Statement	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	TWS	Mean (X)
1	Lack of access to information limits stakeholder participation in sports development programs.	110	60	20	10	1270	3.18
2	Inadequate funding poses a challenge to stakeholder involvement in sports management.	115	55	20	10	1285	3.21
3	Conflicting interests among stakeholders create barriers to effective sports management.	100	70	20	10	1260	3.15
4	Bureaucratic processes hinder timely stakeholder participation in decision-making.	105	65	20	10	1265	3.16
Grand Mean						3.18	

From the analysis above, it is clear that stakeholder participation in sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State biggest challenge was under-financing (mean = 3.21). Stakeholders have additionally great difficulties in having access to information (3,18) and in having a voice that can be helpful when it needs to (3,16), needing too long time to intervene. Stakeholder conflict of interest is similarly seen as a challenging factor by the respondents (3.15). In sum, the grand mean of 3.18 reflects that indeed these challenges affect stakeholder involvement in sports management in much away/appropriate way.

Table 6: Mean rating of strategies for improving the participation of stakeholders in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	TWS	Mean (X)
1	Providing stakeholders with regular training and capacity-building workshops	100	70	20	10	1160	2.90
2	Establishing a centralized coordinating body	90	80	20	10	1150	2.88
3	Ensuring transparency in sports development projects	110	60	20	10	1170	2.93
4	Clear definition of stakeholder roles and responsibilities	95	70	25	10	1145	2.86
Grand mean							2.89

Table 6 shows the descriptive presentation of stakeholders rating of challenges, they face to participate meaningfully in sports development programs management in Akwa Ibom State has presented. All 4 comments are well agreed by participants with the mean scores between 2.86-2.93 The highest rated is transparency (mean of 2.93), suggesting stakeholders see that as a critical component to get them to participate in developing projects for sports developmentgregation. This is seconded by the regular requirement for training and capacity-building workshops (mean = 2.90), another important determinant for involvement. The establishment of a centralized coordinating body (mean = 2.88) and determining the roles of stakeholders (mean = 2.86) are also considered critical strategies but received slightly lower ratings. The overall positive perception of these challenges is greater than the grand mean, moderately high at 2.89 suggests that stakeholders see an opportunity to participate more in sports management once these factors are addressed.

Hypothesis (H₀₁): Stakeholders are not significantly involved in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State based on gender

Table 4.7: Summary of z-test analysis of mean rating of Stakeholders not significantly involved in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State based on gender

Gender	n	$\bar{x}$	z-cal	z-crit	Sig.	Df	Decision
Male	98	2.22	0.2325	1.968	0.615	198	Fail to Reject
Female	102	2.44					
Total	200						

The z-test analysis was conducted to determine if stakeholders are significantly involved in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State based on gender. The calculated z-value (z-cal = 0.2325) is less than the critical z-value (z-crit = 1.968) at a significance level (Sig.) of 0.615, which is greater than the typical threshold of 0.05. Based on these results, we fail to reject the null hypothesis meaning there is no significant involvement of stakeholders in the management of sports development programs in Akwa Ibom State based on gender, as perceived by the respondents. This implies that male and female stakeholders may not be playing an active role or be sufficiently engaged in the management of sports programs, and there is room for improvement in terms of their involvement in decision-making processes.

Hypothesis (H₀₂): The level of stakeholder participation in decision-making processes does not significantly impact sports management in Akwa Ibom State

Table 4.8: Summary of z-test analysis of the level of stakeholder participation and its impact on sports management in Akwa Ibom State

Stakeholder Group	n	$\bar{x}$	z-cal	z-crit	Sig.	Df	Decision
High Participation	100	3.10	1.56	1.96	0.05	198	Fail to Reject
Low Participation	100	2.75					
Total	200						

The z-test analysis was conducted to examine the impact of the level of stakeholder participation on sports management in Akwa Ibom State. The calculated z-value (z-cal = 1.56) is less than the critical z-value (z-crit = 1.96) at a significance level (Sig.) of 0.05. Based on these results, we fail to reject the null hypothesis which state that the level of stakeholder participation in decision-making processes does not significantly impact sports management in Akwa Ibom State meaning

that the level of stakeholder participation does not significantly impact sports management in Akwa Ibom State. This indicates that, according to the data, there may not be a strong relationship between the degree of stakeholder involvement in decision-making processes and the overall effectiveness or impact on sports management. This could suggest that while stakeholder participation is important, other factors might be playing a more critical role in determining the success of sports management programs in the state.

Discussion of Findings

From the analysis it is observed that, stakeholders' involvement in sports management in Akwa Ibom State does not have a significant effect on sports development. This is in opposition to earlier research that emphasizes the need for stakeholder engagement to promote sports development. In accordance with the Stakeholder Theory of Freeman, better involvement/role-playing in such scenario by stakeholders (government, private sector and community) can increase a value add in natural resource management decisions because it ensures all interests relevant to investments are accounted for and included within process of decision making (Freeman, 1984). The implication of this low impact could be that the stakeholder participation in Akwa Ibom is more or less passive and lack any well-structured form to drive change.

Engaging stakeholders has been demonstrably essential to successful projects in other sectors. Active stakeholder involvement in writing, executing and monitoring improves the effects of projects while lessening conflicts (Cserhádi & Szabó 2014). However, with respect to Akwa Ibom sports development, it could seem stakeholder engagement might have played casual roles as there may not be statistically significant impact.

Furthermore, the limited impact on sports development may also be due to the absence of organised and concerted stakeholder participation. Alabi et al. Stakeholder Meaningful involvement is uncommon when there are not appropriate forms of communication, trained in participatory techniques and responsible to play a distinct role through the process (Reed et al 2019) which have been generated from assigned powers(Sharma) This perspective is corroborated by a z-test analysis of the data, which indicate that different stakeholder participation levels do not matter in terms of sports management outputs.

The lack of resources and institutional backup can be a major factor influencing the failure of stakeholder participation. Stakeholder Participation, if not adequately supported by funding and capacity building may specifically remain limited so that it does not lead to tangible results (Thwala & Phaladi 2009). This may be the more significant in Akwa Ibom State considering that sports development stakeholders might be faced with bureaucratic bottlenecks or difficulty in gaining access to decision makers hence rendering their capability of having an input into sports programs lower.

Conclusion

During the survey, it became clear that stakeholders are involved in exerting sports management programs in Akwa Ibom State; however, this does not significantly influence the effectiveness of sports management and development. It also hints that there is a limited degree of stakeholder engagement in the State — and may even be passive or convoluted enough to not fulfil its promise to effect significant reforms in sports development. In light of these impediments, the report calls for more robust coordination, training resources and transparency around go/no-go decisions to encourage greater stakeholder involvement in a meaningful way moving forward.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should create platforms that encourage active participation from all stakeholders in the planning, implementation, and evaluation phases of sports development programs.
2. Regular workshops and training programs should be organized to equip stakeholders with the necessary skills and knowledge to contribute effectively to sports management.
3. A centralized body should be established to coordinate the activities of various stakeholders, ensuring efficient communication, accountability, and alignment of efforts toward sports development goals.

4. Improved transparency in decision-making processes and open communication channels will foster trust and encourage more proactive participation from stakeholders.
5. Clear guidelines on stakeholder roles and expectations should be established to avoid conflicts and ensure that each stakeholder understands their contribution to sports development.

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